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TEACHING BUSINESS ENGLISH TO FUTURE PHILOLOGISTS IN THE REGIME OF DISTANCE EDUCATION

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The article is devoted to solving organizational, didactic and methodical problems of teaching business English to philological students in the regime of distance education. The aim of the article is improving methodical accompaniment of teaching business English to future philologists. The goals of the research are to attract English teachers' attention to the necessity of encouraging students to use regular lexicon in private online communication and enforce the interdiscipline coordination in teaching business English, lexicology and linguistic local lore study. Such methods of research as content analysis of pedagogical literature on the subject, questionnaire, generalization of various viewpoints concerning distance learning were used. Special attention should be paid to methodical accompaniment of teaching business English in online regime. It means that teachers should pay more attention to using productive ways of organizing classes under the condition of distance education. Students should create presentations, situational monologues after watching video clips, which represent abstracts from real business communication, reproduce telephone conversations with the help of formal speech patterns, given in the textbooks. Students should be exercised in writing business letters, answering reclamations etc. Methodical accompaniment requires keeping certain principles: interconnected teaching all kinds of speech activity (reading, speaking, listening, writing); dominant role of exercises; principle of culturological education. The necessity of keeping in mind social and linguistic cultural differences in communicating a native and a foreign language is also grounded by the author. Students' answers to the questionnaire concerning their attitude towards distance learning and business English online show that most of them (88 %) are satisfied with such a way of studying. They also want more attention to be paid to understanding native speakers, telephone conversations, creating advertising production

Keywords: business English, distance education, methodical accompaniment, methodical principles

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1. Introduction

Distance education has become the norm in higher education for the past two years in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. Prior to the pandemic, scientists and educators discussed the issue of so-called "blended learning", which involved combining classroom activities with students' independent work using computer technology. It is difficult to say how much more time would be spent on finding out the advantages and disadvantages of such training, but the reality has changed: in a short period of time, university professors have been forced to switch to distance learning.

Distance learning with all its organizational, didactic, methodological and other problems proved to be effective, productive and accessible. Both teachers and students appreciated its benefits, found ways to use its hidden opportunities; it encouraged them to seek new approaches to education, increased the proportion of students' independent work, and taught them to use computers to solve many problems.

2. Literary review

Many scientific works of Ukrainian scientists are devoted to the problems of distance education: V. Bykov studied the theoretical and methodological principles of modeling the learning environment in the context of information technology and learning tools [1], A. Kozlovsky, Y. Panochyshyn, B. Pogrischuk took care of the use of computer technology and information technologies in the educational process [2], N. Fominykh developed technological, didactic and social characteristics of WEB – 2.0 for teaching English [3], R. Gryshkova's attention was focused on pedagogical problems of distance learning of English in the professional field [4]. At the same time, it should be noted, that distance learning of philology students has its own specifics, as the formation of foreign language communicative competence is associated with the use of not only monologue but also dialogic speech, which seems not very convenient in online classes: student dialogues in ZOOM, Skype or Google team lose naturalness, need a lot of time.

Foreign students E. Frendo [5], P. Emmerson [6], M. Wright and Ukrainian methodologists studied the issues of teaching students of business English philology from different points of view. O. Zabolotskaya, a representative of the Kherson Methodical School believes that "new information technologies can become a means, by which human consciousness acquires a new character: the ability to model a situation using a computer will lead to the development of systems thinking", especially needed to acquire foreign language business communication skills. [7]. The researcher of learning theory is convinced that "computerization of the educational process is a priority for the development of higher education" [8]. The Computer Assistant Learning and Tutoring Systems programs, developed in the west, created the conditions for managing the educational process and receiving feedback from students. Other scholars-methodologists drew attention to the need to adhere to the "principle of cultural education" to overcome the cultural barrier in the process of mastering business English [9, 10]. However, in the process of learning online, many issues, related to the computerization of the educational process, came to the surface, as students began to spend more time on social networks, communicate with each other in informal chats, and so on. English scientists from the University of Cambridge offered "blended learning" [11] and developed a TCT course [12]. American scientists see computerization as a way to educational reform [13]. In Poland, computer tests have been developed for those who study English as a second language [14, 15].

The standard English language, taught to future philologists, in informal use was overloaded with irregular vocabulary, acronyms, slang and jargon, which showed the analysis of student posts on social networks and their answers to the questionnaire on foreign language communication on Twitter, Face book, Tick-talk. Therefore, the question arose about the need to distinguish between normative English for business communication and colloquial language for use in everyday private communication in oral and written forms.

3. Research aim and tasks

The aim of the article is to improve the methodological support of learning English, which means focusing the teacher's efforts on the use of productive ways of organizing classes in distance education.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. To improve methodological support in teaching business English based on methodological principles.
2. To prove the need to take into account sociolinguistic and cultural differences in communication in business English and Ukrainian.

4. Materials and methods

The study was conducted in the period of 2020–2021 on the basis of the Mukachevo University and the Petro Mohyla Black Sea National University.

In order to find out the attitude of students to distance education and to studying business English online, a survey of sophomores was conducted, which was attended by 27 students of CO (ML) 2 group, Mukachevo University and 32 students of the Faculty of Philology of the Black Sea National University, named after Petro

Mohyla: 59 persons, informational consent was obtained from all study participants in accordance with their statements. The survey was conducted in October–November 2021.

Research methods: content analysis of scientific papers on the research topic to identify problematic issues that need to be resolved. Generalization of the existing positions of scientists on distance education and learning of business English to identify the general attitude of the pedagogical community to the teaching of business English in distance philological education. Questionnaire of philology students in order to find out their attitude to learning English and learning online.

Statistical method of compiling and grouping student survey materials to process survey results.

5. Research results

Learning business English requires compliance with certain requirements that change in accordance with the transformations in the global business space, which is constantly affected by computerization and digitalization of all spheres of public life. At the same time, there are provisions that remain unchanged in all circumstances of the use of business English: it is an official language that connects business people, helps to establish useful connections in the professional sphere, to expand the circle of acquaintances with related business representatives.

The peculiarities of the vocabulary of business English communication, which is contained in each textbook on Business English and on the Internet, have not been studied in this paper.

However, there are generally accepted rules for doing business, which provide awareness of the difference between formal and informal communication, which requires:

- avoid slang, jargon, dubious expressions, inappropriate comparisons, colloquialisms, verbosity;
- preliminary elaboration of possible options for concessions that you are ready to make in order to resolve the disputed issue;
- use of official language constructions, which creates conditions for confident sound during speeches and presentations;
- refusal to use abbreviations: examination, not exam; cell phone, not just cell; television instead of telly or TV.
- the ability to listen carefully to the interlocutor, not to interrupt him/her, to ask not rhetorical questions, but those that require a specific answer;
- empathy, i.e. the ability to put yourself in the place of the interlocutor and predict his/her reaction to your statement.

The practice of teaching business English shows that these rules should be constantly reminded, as students, studying remotely, get used to informal communication and inadvertently transfer the skills of such online correspondence in the academic sphere. Moreover, when studying remotely, it is necessary to organize as many exercises and other types of work as possible, where students would constantly practice the use of business vocabulary.

The results of the survey of 2nd year students, studying business English, showed that 94 % of them have no practical experience of using Business English, which we perceive as a completely natural phenomenon, given the age

of students and the fact that they are only in their second year. But the vast majority of students in the process of mastering business English would like to learn to write

business letters, communicate by phone, develop promotional products, understand the interlocutor-native speaker. The results of the survey are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Distribution of answers to the questionnaire for 2nd year students studying business English

No.	Questions	Answers in %		
		yes	no	Difficult to answer
1	Are you satisfied with learning online?	88	7	5
2	Do you think it is necessary to communicate in normative English on social networks?	76	19	5
3	Do you use profanity and other deviations from language standards in private communication?	21	79	–
4	Is it easy for you to switch from conversational to business English?	75	22	3
5	Do you have experience in using business English in practice?	6	94	-
6	Which aspect of mastering business English do you find most problematic? talking, speech perception by ear, writing	16		
		58		
		26		
7	What would you like to learn more in business English? write business letters, talk on the phone development of advertising products understand the native speaker	56		
		89		
		92		
		67		
8.	Do knowledge of linguistics and awareness of socio-cultural values of native speakers help you to better master the teaching material of business English?	82	6	12

We would like to draw your attention to the methodological support of teaching English to students of philology, which means the teacher's efforts to use productive ways of organizing classes in distance education: encouraging students to create presentations, situational monologues after watching videos with excerpts from real business communication, reproduction of telephone conversations using clichés, provided in the textbook, writing business letters, responding to complaints, etc. Methodical support requires compliance with certain methodological principles:

- the principle of interconnected learning of all types of speech activity (reading, speaking, listening and writing);
- the dominant role of exercises;
- approximations;
- taking into account the native language;
- the principle of culturological education.

In the context of distance education, the principle of interconnected learning of all types of speech activity (reading, speaking, listening and writing) is somewhat transformed: more attention is paid to reading, listening and writing business letters, business documents, etc.; speaking is mostly monologue except for the imitation of a telephone conversation. The role of organizing business games is enhanced when students share the roles of partners, product suppliers or service professionals, and use the simulation method to reproduce business communication.

The principle of the dominant role of exercises is designed to provide multiple exercises in the use of official language constructions, clichés common in the business field, stamps for writing business letters and other business documents. The vast majority of exercises should be productive, i.e. encourage students to create their own product: write an appeal to partners, enter into a contract for the

supply of certain products, give a reasoned response to complaints, and so on.

Adherence to the principle of approximation involves modeling of various situations of business communication in the classroom, as close as possible to the conditions of real business: preparation of presentations, development of promotional products, negotiations. Based on the principles of interdisciplinary coordination, teaching dialogic speech in the course of general English, lexicology and linguistic local lore studies should help to form appropriate competencies for business communication. Attention should also be paid to the observance of political correctness, punctuality, responsibility and style of execution of various documents.

Taking into account the native language in the course of teaching business communication not only promotes awareness of language differences in native and foreign languages, but also focuses students' attention on socio-cultural differences of different nationalities, which should be taken into account in building partnerships.

Particular attention should be paid to the principle of culturological education, which involves students' mastering the need to take into account intercultural differences in lifestyles, priorities, values, ways of doing business, manner of communicative behavior in different countries. Students should be helped to intensify their knowledge of the field of local lore and try to rely on them in the process of business games, presentations and other types of business communication.

The cultural component is extremely important for establishing and maintaining business relationships with partners in different countries.

Methodological support of learning English in distance education should help students master the basics of business communication and prepare them for real English-language business cooperation with representatives of other nationalities who use English as the language of international communication.

A limitation of the study is that it was conducted during 2020–2021.

Further explorations in the field of business English in distance education are related to the development of specific examples of intercultural communication in English with people from different cultures who use English as an international language to establish international contacts and solve business problems.

6. Conclusions

1. The methodological support of the process of acquiring knowledge and skills of intercultural communication based on methodological principles, which

are essentially the answer to the question "How to organize the educational process?", should be improved in the teaching of business English in distance education. Distance education with all its organizational, didactic and methodological problems still creates additional conditions for students to master the rules and vocabulary of business English, as they have more time to do homework, almost unlimited access to Internet resources.

2. Taking into account socio-linguistic differences in business English and Ukrainian, as well as the difference between formal and everyday communication will help students adapt more quickly to the new imaginary business environment, where there are rules, etiquette, manner of communicative behavior.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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